

The Development of a Clothing Sizing System for Benghazi Older Adults Based on Anthropometric Data

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ABSTRACT:

A clothing sizing system designed to analyze body type differences is the most effective approach for determining the most suitable sizes in clothing design. This system organizes a specific population into homogeneous subgroups based on key body dimensions, ensuring that individuals within the same subgroup share similar body shape characteristics. Anthropometric data is vital for the development of this sizing system.

The objective of this project is to examine anthropometric measurements of individuals and analyze them using simple statistical methods to understand the body ranges and variations across different genders and age groups for the development of a sizing system. Nineteen body dimensions were measured for each participant, with data collected from 60 older adults (30 males and 30 females aged 50 to 65) in Benghazi.

The anthropometric data were analyzed using t-tests and ANOVA to identify differences based on age and gender. The t-test results indicated significant differences in most body measurements, except for four: head circumference, arm circumference, shoulder-to-waist length, and knee circumference. The ANOVA results showed no significant differences in most measurements, except for waist-to-hip length and outside leg length in males, as well as hip circumference and weight in females.

Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to assess the relationships between various body measurements. The analysis revealed a strong correlation between weight and height with several other dimensions. Mean values and standard deviations were used to establish size categories for the size chart, which identified three sizes: L (large), M (medium), and S (small).

Keywords: Clothing sizing system, Anthropometric data, Benghazi older adults, Pearson correlation, Age and gender variations, Statistical analysis.

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INTRODUCTION

The development of clothing sizing systems is crucial for ensuring that garments fit properly and provide comfort to the wearer. This necessity is particularly pronounced for older adults, whose body dimensions can vary considerably from those of younger populations. In Benghazi, Libya, there is a growing demand to establish a sizing system specifically designed for the elderly, grounded in precise anthropometric data.

Anthropometric measurements involve the systematic collection of data on body dimensions, which can be utilized to develop sizing systems that accurately reflect the physical characteristics of a given population. Prior research has shown that leveraging anthropometric data to create sizing systems can lead to better-fitting clothing, thus enhancing user comfort and satisfaction [1].

This study aims to gather and analyze anthropometric data from elderly individuals in Benghazi. The objective is to develop a clothing sizing system tailored to the specific needs of this demographic. This approach is expected to not only improve clothing fit and comfort but also support the local garment industry by providing a scientifically based framework for size standardization [2].

The methodology includes measuring various body dimensions of elderly participants, such as height, weight, chest circumference, waist circumference, and hip circumference. These measurements will be subjected to statistical analysis to identify common patterns and variations. The resultant data will be used to formulate a sizing chart suitable for adoption by local clothing manufacturers [3].

By addressing the specific needs of the elderly population in Benghazi, this research contributes to the broader field of apparel design and sizing systems. It highlights the significance of utilizing localized anthropometric data to develop clothing that fits well and meets the comfort requirements of the target population [4].

LITERATURE REVIEWS

This section includes a summary of a few selected anthropometric studies. Some of the methods and techniques used in these previous studies have been adopted in the present study. These studies were conducted to obtain anthropometric measurements of the human body, such as height, weight, waist, chest, hip, etc. It was found that there are anthropometric differences among people caused by ethnicity/race, age, gender, and the dimension of time. The anthropometric differences related to age and gender have been studied in several research projects using different statistical tests.

Some Study that People Made in Clothing Sizing System for Children and Adults

The aim of this paper was to examine anthropometric measurements for students in grades four, five, and six in the basic education stage. The study focused on collecting body measurements of school children in Benghazi and analyzing them using simple statistical methods. This analysis would help determine the body ranges and variations present among students in these three grades, ultimately aiding in the development of a sizing system for these grades.

The method used to analyze the data collected from different schools involved Minitab software. ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis tests were employed to identify differences between age groups. The sample consisted of a total of 180 Libyan primary students (90 male and 90 female), with 30 students from each grade. The students were aged between 9 and 11 years, and the sample was randomly selected from public and private schools in Benghazi. The results confirmed that there are differences in most body measurements, except for arm height and waist-to-hip height. These

differences were taken into consideration when establishing the sizing system. From these findings, it can be concluded that weight is very strongly correlated with several dimensions. Height and weight measurements were used as guides to determine the dimensions of garments. The mean values and standard deviations were applied to develop size increments for the size chart, which identified three size categories: L (Large), M (Medium), and S (Small). The conclusions drawn from the study indicate that there are significant differences in some anthropometric measurements among children from different age groups for almost all measurements, as well as between genders for certain measurements [5].

In another study, the objective was to establish and analyze the physical measurements of students aged 6 to 17 years in both primary and secondary school stages. ANOVA and other statistical tests were utilized to assess differences.

The measurements were applied to create various types of clothing, such as school uniforms. ANOVA analysis was used to determine differences between age groups. The results indicated that there are no significant differences in most anthropometric measurements between genders, suggesting that these differences would not significantly impact the production of clothing suitable for children of different genders.

The t-test results indicated significant differences in anthropometric measurements between genders for age groups 12 to 17 years. It was concluded that all measurements show significant differences except for arm circumference in the 6-11 age group. However, there are no significant differences between age groups (12-17) for all measurements among male students.

The main perspective that clothing producers should consider is size. They need to recognize the specific sizes required to create their garments. Therefore, size improvements should align with their methods to deliver accurate sizes that fit the consumer's body, especially children [6].

The research also investigated fit-related issues for Indian males, aiming to develop standardized body sizes for lower garments. The methodology involved a sample of 2,401 Indian participants from six different locations, aged between 18 and 29, with the aim of developing a clothing sizing system for the lower body.

The study concluded that designing an accurate and well-fitting sizing system for Indian bottom wear is essential. Useful data and analysis should be performed to improve consumer comfort [7].

This work discusses the creation of a clothing sizing system tailored for adults in Benghazi, Libya. The study aims to address the lack of appropriate sizing standards by collecting and analyzing anthropometric data, including measurements such as height, weight, and body circumferences from a sample of Benghazi adults. Using statistical methods, the researchers identified key variations in body dimensions across different demographics. The findings highlight significant differences in measurements based on age and gender, which are crucial for developing a sizing system that accurately fits the local population. The resulting sizing system is intended to enhance the comfort and fit of clothing for Benghazi adults, ultimately improving consumer satisfaction and guiding manufacturers in the production of locally appropriate garments. The study underscores the importance of using region-specific data to create effective sizing solutions [2].

The article addresses the creation of a clothing sizing system tailored specifically for schoolgirls in Benghazi, utilizing anthropometric measurements. It details the methods employed to gather body measurements from a representative sample of schoolgirls, focusing on various dimensions, including height, weight, bust, waist, and hip sizes. Through statistical analysis, the study uncovers significant variations in body measurements among different age groups and sizes, underscoring the need for a customized sizing system that accurately reflects the population's unique traits. The goal is to enhance the fit and comfort of clothing for schoolgirls, thereby improving their overall experience in educational environments. Ultimately, the article emphasizes the importance of integrating local anthropometric data into clothing design to better meet the needs of students in Benghazi [3].

Research consistently shows that body dimensions vary significantly across different age groups. Studies such as [4] have demonstrated that children and adolescents experience distinct growth patterns that impact their body proportions. Specifically, height, weight, and girth measurements tend to differ markedly between early and late adolescents, highlighting the need for age-specific sizing charts. This variability is particularly pronounced in schoolchildren, where growth spurts during these developmental years necessitate regular updates to sizing standards. The literature highlights the critical importance of utilizing anthropometric data to develop clothing sizing charts tailored for specific age groups and regional contexts. The study of seventh, eighth, and ninth-grade students in Benghazi is particularly timely, as it aims to provide localized data that can directly inform clothing manufacturers and educators. By focusing on the unique physical characteristics of Benghazi schoolchildren, this research seeks to enhance the comfort and fit of school uniforms, ultimately contributing to the students' overall well-being and academic success.

Some Study that People Made in Clotting Sizing System for Elderly

The purpose of this study is to propose a specialized clothing sizing system for elderly obese Korean women aged 60 to 79. The data used in this study was taken from the fifth Korean Agency for Technology and Standards (2004).

The method employed to analyze the physical characteristics of obese elderly women included measurements of height (6 items), girth (11 items), width (5 items), and direct measurements, totaling 38 items. This included 6 items for thickness, 9 items for length, and weight. A t-test was performed to obtain the mean and standard deviation to compare the physical characteristics of normal and obese body types. Additionally, body mass index (BMI) measurements were utilized for individuals with a BMI over 25.

The findings revealed that the lower bodies of elderly obese women tend to be shorter and wider than average. In particular, their torsos from the chest to the waist are generally more obese than in other areas. According to the Korean standard measurement (KS) guidelines, the clothing sizing system establishes size intervals as follows: 5 cm in stature, 5 cm and 3 cm in bust measurements, 3 cm in waist, and 3 cm in hip circumference. This system is based on dualistic distribution.

The study concluded that older obese women had shorter lower bodies with larger circumference, width, and thickness compared to those with a normal body type. The characteristics of the elderly obese body type were defined to create a customized sizing system in accordance with the KS standards, targeting specific brands that cater to elderly obese women [8].

In another study, a detailed apparel sizing system was proposed for brands targeting elderly men aged 60 to 79 by examining body type differences within this age group. Based on data from the fifth Korean Anthropometric Survey, the researchers compared the body measurements of middle-aged men with those of elderly men.

The method used to analyze the data included criteria for determining obesity and the number of study subjects according to the obesity index. The study established sizing by measuring heights between 160 cm and 170 cm and chest measurements ranging from 85 cm to 100 cm for casual tops. For suit tops, a total of 11 sizes were defined, with heights between 160 cm and 170 cm and chest measurements from 88 cm to 100 cm. For bottoms, detailed sizes were suggested by dividing basic and reference areas, resulting in 13 sizes with waist circumferences between 84 cm and 94 cm, and hip circumferences between 90 cm and 98 cm.

Mean, standard deviation, and t-tests were employed to compare elderly men with middle-aged men (ages 40 to 59). The researchers concluded that the pattern design should be tailored to fit ready-to-wear clothing for elderly men, as this could enhance overall satisfaction. The total coverage for the bottoms in the study was 34.7%. The research results are based on the target demographic of older males, providing a clearer understanding of their characteristics through an age-specific system [9].

The literature underscores the critical need for anthropometric studies to inform the development of clothing size charts for adults. By utilizing localized data, researchers and manufacturers can create garments that cater to the specific body dimensions and cultural preferences of the population. This approach not only enhances fit and comfort but also fosters a positive consumer experience,

ultimately benefiting the clothing industry and its clientele. Further research in this area will continue to illuminate the relationship between body measurements and clothing design, leading to improved standards in apparel manufacturing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section offers a comprehensive overview of the materials and methods utilized in this study.

Participants

A sample of 60 participants was selected for this study. The sample was randomly chosen from public places in Benghazi during 2022/2023. An equal number of adults (30 males and 30 females) were measured within the age group of 55 to 65 years. Table 1 provides a summary of the number of adults surveyed.

Table 1. Summary of Data Collected and Age and Gender of Participants

Gender / age	Age range						Total
	50 to 55		55 to 60		60 to 65		
Place taken from	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Relative and family and neighbor	10	10	10	10	10	10	60
Total	20		20		20		60

The Body Measurements

Twenty-eight anthropometric dimensions typically utilized in clothing design were identified for establishing sizing systems. However, only nineteen of these dimensions were selected for creating sizing systems specifically for older adults, as referenced in previous studies [10] and [6] and detailed in Table 2. Participants were advised to wear light clothing for precise measurements and to take off their shoes when measuring height and weight. The measurements were collected using an anthropometric kit (Rosscraft Centurion Kit), as shown in Fig. 1 [5].

Figure 1. Rosscraft Centurion Kit

Table 2. The Anthropometric Dimension that Used in Study

No	Body Dimension	Definition
1	Weight	the amount or quantity of heaviness or mass, amount a thing weights
2	Height	the longest extent of anything as measured from end to end
3	Head circumference	Is a measurement of a head around its largest area? It measures the distance from above the eyebrows and ears and around the back of the head
4	Neck circumference	measurement is taken immediately above the thyroid cartilage
5	Waist circumference	is a measurement taken around the abdomen at the level of the belly button
6	Chest circumference	the horizontal circumference taken just above the nipples during a period of quiet breathing
7	Hip circumference	measure the largest circumference around hips and butt
8	Arm circumference	is the circumference of arm measured at the mid-point between the tip of the shoulder and the tip of the elbow
9	Shoulder to shoulder length	start the end of the tape on the outside edge of the shoulder where you want the shirt to start, this is where the horizontal part of the shoulder meets the vertical part of the arm measure up over the curve of the shoulders and to outside edge of the other shoulder
10	Shoulder to wrist length	from the tip of the shoulder to about 0.5cm below the wrist bone
11	Shoulder to waist length	shoulder same straight down to the waist
12	Front body length	While standing as straight, measure from the center of your neckline, in between the collar bone, down to your waist (slightly below your navel)
13	Back body length	From the nape of the neck to the natural waist line From the nape of the neck to the natural waist line
14	Waist to hips length	Is the ratio of the length of the waist to that of the hips
15	Shoulder length	From neck out to the tip of the shoulder
16	Front body width	The HPS is the high point of your shoulder. It is the seam on the shirt that is stitched from the sleeve to the collar on both sides.
17	Back body width	Measure from the side seam under the arm across the back to the other side seam under the arm
18	Knee circumference	While standing straight, measure around the circumference of the knee joint
19	Outside leg length	pants external stitch length (i.e. length from belt to ankle)

Source: [7] [5] [4] [3]

Anthropometric Data Analysis

After conducting the anthropometric survey, the data obtained from this study served as the basis for analysis. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (Minitab) Version 17.1 was used for data input and analysis. Descriptive statistics, including mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation, were calculated using Microsoft Excel to summarize the collected data. Subsequently, ANOVA, t-tests, and Pearson correlation coefficient analyses were conducted to develop the sizing system. The objectives of each test were as follows: ANOVA was used to identify differences between age groups, while t-tests were employed to determine differences between genders. Additionally, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to assess the interrelationships among various body measurements. The results from these tests were used to develop the clothing sizing system, as explained later [11], [5], [4], [3], [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

The normality test was used to determine whether the collected data were well modeled by a normal distribution. As expected, the data for all measurements followed a normal distribution. The mean and standard deviation for all measurements for both males and females are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. The Mean and Standard Deviation (male) By Age

Body Dimension	Descriptive Statistics	age for male		
		50 to 55	56 to 60	61 to 65
1. weight	Mean	68.42	73.5	75.56
	St. division	5.03	8.85	6.35
2. Height	Mean	175.31	175.17	175.68
	St. division	4.17	3.12	4.10
3. Head circumference	Mean	55.56	54.74	54.67
	St. division	1.45	1.80	2.41
4. Neck circumference	Mean	36.57	37.11	37.87
	St. division	0.86	3.33	2.30
5. Waist circumference	Mean	89.76	88.51	88.77
	St. division	2.35	2.63	3.74
6. Chest circumference	Mean	91.47	91.67	91.25
	St. division	2.53	2.90	4.90
7. Hip circumference	Mean	94.68	93.08	91.31
	St. division	3.13	1.51	5.37
8. Arm circumference	Mean	30.08	29.17	32.50
	St. division	1.80	1.87	3.97
9. Shoulder to shoulder length	Mean	43.27	42.92	44.12
	St. division	1.43	1.20	2.72
10. Shoulder to wrist length	Mean	56.7	57.3	57.86
	St. division	0.88	2.64	3.60
11. Shoulder to waist length	Mean	32.75	33.02	35.04
	St. division	2.59	3.24	3.62
12. Front body length	Mean	53.51	54.51	54.21
	St. division	2.66	2.83	4.77
13. Back body length	Mean	53.3	54.01	53.74
	St. division	2.31	2.43	4.98
14. Waist to hips length	Mean	14.75	17.71	19.54
	St. division	0.77	4.62	3.18
15. Shoulder length	Mean	20.91	21.60	22.22
	St. division	0.97	1.87	1.51
16. Front body width	Mean	46.56	48.42	50.30
	St. division	1.39	3.45	3.01
17. Back body width	Mean	46.4	48.3	50.03
	St. division	1.56	3.23	3.13
18. knee circumference	Mean	37.17	36.38	38.32
	St. division	1.80	2.88	2.94
19. Outside leg length	Mean	101.83	97.21	95.80
	St. division	2.22	5.34	4.16

Table 4. The Mean and Standard Deviation (female) By Age

Body Dimension	Descriptive Statistics	age for female		
		50 to 55	56 to 60	61 to 65
1. weight	Mean	76.98	68.96	66.89
	St. division	7.50	3.58	7.31
2. Height	Mean	162.26	161.02	162.14
	St. division	2.30	3.37	3.67
3. Head circumference	Mean	55.3	53.91	54.15
	St. division	1.30	0.65	2.40
4. Neck circumference	Mean	35.77	35.34	36.68
	St. division	1.13	1.89	2.46
5. Waist circumference	Mean	94.1	91.77	92.82
	St. division	2.279	2.33	9.29
6. Chest circumference	Mean	107.42	102.57	100.10
	St. division	3.70	3.27	8.29
7. Hip circumference	Mean	109.5	104.35	102.94
	St. division	4.24	2.80	7.54
8. Arm circumference	Mean	31.73	27.14	30.21
	St. division	2.65	2.07	4.84
9. Shoulder to shoulder length	Mean	43.25	40.64	42.27
	St. division	2.08	2.13	2.86
10. Shoulder to wrist length	Mean	54.66	54.328	53.81
	St. division	1.32	1.01	3.943
11. Shoulder to waist length	Mean	36.625	34.14	33.35
	St. division	3.11	2.95	3.075
12. Front body length	Mean	51.36	50.57	49.14
	St. division	4.90	4.72	6.28
13. Back body length	Mean	50.5	49.11	49.06
	St. division	4.85	4.25	6.300
14. Waist to hips length	Mean	14.46	14.77	16.38
	St. division	0.907	1.78	2.07
15. Shoulder length	Mean	20.36	19.85	20.48
	St. division	0.85	1.21	1.53
16. Front body width	Mean	47.18	46.17	45.44
	St. division	1.33	0.92	3.18
17. Back body width	Mean	47.48	46.02	45.33
	St. division	1.27	1.416	3.38
18. knee circumference	Mean	38.61	37.74	37.52
	St. division	1.71	1.44	3.84
19. Outside leg length	Mean	87.33	85.87	86.51
	St. division	4.86	4.62	4.03

Differences of Anthropometric Measurements by gender (T-test)

The results of the t-test indicate that almost all anthropometric measurements show significant differences between the genders of the respondents. These differences should be considered when designing clothing sizing systems for older adults. However, the table presents measurements that do not show significant differences. These anthropometric measurements include head

circumference, arm circumference, shoulder-to-waist length, and knee circumference (as shown in Table 5). These differences will not be considered in the design of the clothing sizing systems [12].

Table 5. Differences of Anthropometric Measurements by t-test

Measurement	P-value	Significant
Head circumference	0.574148997	Not Sig.
Arm circumference	0.599719783	Not Sig.
Shoulder to waist length	0.578637517	Not sig.
Knee circumference	0.714866548	Not sig.

Differences in Anthropometric Measurements by Age (ANOVA)

Differences in Anthropometric Measurements by Age for Males (ANOVA)

Table 6 indicates that there are no significant differences in anthropometric measurements among the various age groups. Consequently, these variations should not influence the design of clothing intended for older adults of different ages.

Nonetheless, the analysis identifies significant differences in specific measurements, such as waist-to-hip length, front body width, and outside leg length. These factors should be considered in the development of clothing sizing systems. This outcome contrasts with earlier studies conducted by [5] [4] [3] [2] [6].

Table 6. Differences of Anthropometric Measurements by Age Groups Male (ANOVA)

Measurements	P-value	Significant
1	0.55	Not significant
2	0.60	Not significant
3	0.58	Not significant
4	0.57	Not significant
5	0.5725	Not significant
6	0.578	Not significant
7	0.67	Not significant
8	0.7014	Not significant
9	0.69	Not significant
10	0.54	Not significant
11	0.54	Not significant
12	0.647	Not significant
13	0.578	Not significant
14	0.08	Significant
15	0.554	Not significant
16	0.21	Significant
17	0.58	Not significant
18	0.64	Not Significant
19	0.47	Significant

Differences in Anthropometric Measurements by Age for Females (ANOVA)

The results of the ANOVA test indicate that almost all anthropometric measurements do not show significant differences ($P\text{-value} < 0.05$) between the ages of respondents, except for weight and hip circumference. These differences should not be considered when designing clothing sizing systems for different age groups (as shown in Table 7). Therefore, these results suggest that age is not a factor influencing the development of the human body in these age groups [12]. This finding contrasts with previous studies conducted by [5] [2] and is in agreement with some studies by [13].

Correlation Analysis

A key measurement should be a body measurement that exhibits strong relationships with most other body dimensions. This selection allowed for the development of a sizing system. The criteria

for identifying key measurements include various established methods. By employing correlation coefficients, it becomes possible to pinpoint these key measurements. The values of correlation coefficients reflect the strength of linear relationships between variables and were utilized in this study. Pearson correlation coefficient analysis was performed to explore the interrelationships among different body measurements. The following points clarify the strength of these relationships: A correlation coefficient of 0.5 or less indicates no relationship. A correlation coefficient between 0.5 and 0.75 signifies a mild relationship. A correlation coefficient of 0.76 or higher denotes a strong relationship [14].

Tables 8 and 9 display the relationships among measurements and present the correlation coefficients for each measurement in relation to the others.

Table 8 indicates that height measurements show strong correlations with head circumference, hip circumference, shoulder-to-wrist length, front body length, back body length, and knee circumference. Additionally, neck circumference measurements are closely related to chest circumference, hip circumference, shoulder-to-wrist length, front body length, back body length, and knee circumference. Arm circumference also exhibits strong relationships with shoulder-to-wrist length, front body length, back body length, and knee circumference. In terms of height, there is a significant correlation with cervical height for males.

For females, the data reveals that weight measurements correlate strongly with shoulder-to-waist length and front body length (as seen in Table 9).

These findings suggest that height is a crucial measurement for males, while weight is a crucial measurement for females. The results align with previous research conducted by [15], [5] [4] [3] [2] [6], [16] and [17] [18], among others.

Table 7. Differences of Anthropometric Measurements by Age Groups Female (ANOVA)

Measurements	P-value	Significant
1	0.24	Significant
2	0.53	Not significant
3	0.645	Not significant
4	0.588	Not significant
5	0.84	Not significant
6	0.58	Not significant
7	0.16	Significant
8	0.59	Not significant
9	0.57	Not significant
10	0.59	Not significant
11	0.98	Not significant
12	0.58	Not significant
13	0.77	Not significant
14	0.697	Not significant
15	0.565	Not significant
16	0.87	Not significant
17	0.787	Not significant
18	0.78	Not significant
19	0.76	Not significant

Development of Size Charts

The development of the size chart was carried out using values obtained from the statistical information based on the (t-test) of body dimensions. The mean values and the *standard deviations were used for creating size steps for the size chart. Therefore, different sizes of clothing for male and female must be developed due to the differences in some measurements between genders. Three sizes were developed: S(small), M(medium) and L(large). These sizes were developed because of there were multiple body shape in each gender group. There is a difference between genders in almost all the anthropometric measurements based on(t-test) analysis. One of the values can be calculated if there is no difference between genders (ages) each dimension. However, two (three) values can be calculated if there is difference between genders (age groups) for that dimensions according to t-test (ANOVA). Table 10 shows the clothing size charts for all body dimensions

Table 8. Correlation Coefficient Measurements for Old Male

Measurement	Strong relationship
2	3, 7, 10, 12, 13,18
3	7,6,12,13
4	6,7,10,12,13,18
7	12,18
8	10,12, 13, 14, 18
9	10
11	12,13
13	14, 18
14	18

Table 9. Correlation Coefficient Measurements for Old Female

Measurement	Strong relationship
1	11,12
2	3
8	16
10	11
16	18

CONCLUSION

The overall goal is to develop a clothing sizing system based on anthropometric measurements. In this study, anthropometric measurements were obtained for older males and females aged 50 to 65 years in Benghazi, Libya. A normality test was used to determine whether the collected data followed a normal distribution. As expected, all measurements followed a normal distribution.

An ANOVA test was conducted to find differences between age groups. The results indicated no significant differences between the age groups, except for waist-to-hip length, front body width, and outside leg length for males, as well as hip circumference and weight for females. However, the t-test revealed differences between genders for most anthropometric measurements, except for head circumference, arm circumference, shoulder-to-waist length, and knee circumference. Pearson correlation coefficients analysis was carried out to determine the interrelationships between various body measurements. (If the correlation coefficient is 0.5, there is no relationship; if the correlation coefficient is between 0.5 and 0.75, there is a mild relationship; and if the correlation coefficient is 0.76 or higher, it indicates a strong relationship). The key dimensions should be those that have the strongest correlations with most other body dimensions. From the results, it can be concluded that height, arm circumference, and neck circumference are key dimensions for males. Moreover, weight is a key dimension for females. Therefore, these measurements should be taken accurately to establish the correct uniform sizing. Tailors and clothing manufacturers must consider gender before creating custom-made clothing. In conclusion, the main aspect that apparel manufacturers need to focus on is clothing size. They must know the exact sizes before producing their garments. Thus, the development of sizes should follow their procedures to produce accurate sizes that fit the consumer's body.

Table 10. Size chart for male and female cm

Measurements	Age	Male and Female					
		S			M		
Head circumference		52		55		58	
Arm circumference		25.2		30.58		35.5	
shoulder to waist length		32.3		38.667		44.9	
knee circumference		32		37		46	
		male			Female		
		S	M	L	S	M	L
Weight in kg	50-55	60	73	86.8	64	76.9	88
	56-60				58	68.9	84
	61-65				52.1	66.8	81
Hip circumference	50-55	86.3	93	100	98.5	109.5	122
	56-60				96	104.3	119
	61-65				88	102.9	117
		Male			Female		
		S	M	L	S	M	L
Waist to hips length	50-55	13	14.75	22	12.2	15.2	19
	56-60	12.4	17.7	27			
	61-65	15.34	19.54	25.74			
Front body width	50-55	44.3	46.5	50	42.18	45.8	49.42
	56-60	44	48.4	55			
	61-65	42.3	50.3	56.3			
Outside leg length	50-55	89.68	101.8	105.5	77.6	86.4	95.3
	56-60	85.3	97.2	107.8			
	61-65	87.2	95.7	104			
		Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
		S	M	L	S	M	L
Height	50-65	168	156.3	175.4	161.7	184.8	168.7
Neck circumference	50-65	34	32.2	37.5	35.4	39.5	42.1
Waist circumference	50-65	81	85.3	88.4	93	97	102.1
Chest circumference	50-65	84.2	93.2	91	103	99.3	113.4
Shoulder to shoulder length	50-65	40.5	36.4	43.7	41.5	48.3	46
Shoulder to wrist length	50-65	53	59.5	57.6	54.2	63	59.3
Front body length	50-65	47.2	40	54	50.3	64	60.7
Back body length	50-65	46.5	39.6	53.7	49.8	63.7	60.3
Shoulder length	50-65	19	17.54	22	20.14	24.8	22.78
Back body width	50-65	43.7	41.2	48	45	52.9	49

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